

REPORT:

A3.2.5

Deliverable D5: “Design document for a new mechanically active on-chip flow pump that will be integrated in a microfluidic device for use as a transfer standard in drug discovery and in organ on a chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min”

This report was written as part of activity A.3.2.5 from the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2019 and focused on providing traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and mixing behaviour and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. For more details about this project, please visit www.drugmetrology.com

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Introduction to the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery project

The overall aim of this project is to improve dosing accuracy and to enable the traceable measurement of volume, flow and pressure in existing drug delivery devices and in-line sensors operating at very low flow rates. This will be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and by expanding the existing metrological infrastructure. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, which are step changes between two flow rates within a second, the physical properties of mixtures of liquids and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results and thus to improve patient safety.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices regarding changes in flow rate, from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids (WP1). For steady flow rates an uncertainty of 1 % ($k=2$) or better is expected, whereas for fast changing flow rates an uncertainty of 2 % ($k=2$) or better is expected. The techniques developed will be used to characterise and validate the different response times of at least 3 different types of drug delivery devices (including infusion analysers) (WP3 and WP4) and one type of flow sensor, to accurately measure the administered flow and volume with the required uncertainties.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the partner NMIs in order to enable the traceable in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure difference, with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$). The measurement uncertainty will be validated using Newtonian liquids with traceable dynamic viscosity calibration. Additionally, tests with non-Newtonian liquids will be performed in order to prove the concept. To calibrate transfer standards for the in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity and other physical properties of liquids, in order to use these transfer standards for flow measurement and to determine the mixing behaviour of different liquids.
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing medical flow devices (e.g. infusion pumps, pain controllers and infusion pump analysers) with traceability to a primary standard and with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$) for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 ml/min and also to develop a proof-of-concept on-chip microfluidic pump used as a transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi-infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration. The flow rates and pressures will be traceably calibrated in all infusion lines, as well as at the outlet of the syringe pump, to be able to analyse the effects of pressure-equalising devices and to detect occlusion phenomena and bad mixing configurations.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organisations (ISO/TC 30, ISO/TC 48, ISO/TC/SC 62D, ISO/TC 69, ISO/TC 76, ISO/TC 84, ISO/TC 150, ISO/TC 210) and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

Activity 3.2.5 – Writing of a design document for the on-chip flow pump

Overall Objective: Using input from A3.2.1-A3.2.4, INESC MN and IPQ and will write a design document for a new mechanically active on-chip flow pump that will be integrated in a microfluidic device for use as a transfer standard in drug discovery and in organ on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.

The following Institutes have contributed to this Deliverable:

no	Participant Type	Short Name	Organisation legal full name	Country
11	External Funded Partner	INESC MN	INESC Microsistemas e Nanotecnologias-Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas de Computadores Para os Microsistemas e as Nanotecnologias	Portugal
1	Internal Funded Partner	IPQ	Instituto Português da Qualidade, I.P.	Portugal

The progress within this report covers the Period from 1st June 2019 to the end of July 2021.

1 – INTRODUCTION

Infusion therapy is the most common form of therapy used in health care. However, the existing infusion devices show flow discrepancies as high as 20.1%, as flow rates decrease to a few nL/min. This contributes to high morbidity and mortality of patients [1]. To tackle this, the MeDDII project aims at the development and characterization of a new on-chip microfluidic pump integrated with microfluidics, foreseen to be used as traceable standard for the calibration of drug delivery devices used in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip technology for flow rate ranges below 100 nL/min. This precisely controlled on-chip micropump can be considered a proof-of-concept and a movable transfer standard to be used on site.

INESC MN developed a Hybrid Microfluidic Pump that can generate low flow rates in a range from (5 to 100) nL/min. The prototype aims at continuous microflow and comprises several materials with optimal mechanical, optical and (bio)chemical properties. The work started with the identification of 3 different types of microfluidic human organ-on-a-chip models. Allometric scaling principles were considered in relation to the types of perfusion movements, media volumes, flow rates, pressure drops, cell numbers, drug concentrations, reaction kinetics, etc. This information was used to assist with the simulation, design and microfabrication of the microfluidic flow pump. The microfluidic pump, chosen to be driven by electroosmotic forces, was then simulated using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.1. The simulation allowed to determine channel and electrode dimensions and position as well as work variables such as imposed voltage range to meet flow rates in the range (5 – 100) nL/min. After determining the design of the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump, the fabrication used a combination of cleanroom micro/nanofabrication techniques and off-the-shelf equipment [2]. The device was initially planned to be characterized by micro particle image velocimetry by THL and HSG MIT (A3.2.6). As is, the flow rate imposed by the Hybrid Microfluidic Pump can be additionally characterized by Gravimetry, Pending Drop and Front Track methods developed within the project. This provides the versatility necessary to assess the traceability of the flow imposed by the Hybrid Microfluidic Pump and to ensure it meets the requirements to be used in organ-on-a-chip devices.

The core of the device was microfabricated onto silicon. Electrodes were defined through photolithography (Heidelberg DWLii, m.f.s. 0.8 μ m, 6") of Al_{98.5}Si_{1.0}Cu_{0.5} (3000Å, by percentage) deposited by magnetron sputtering (Nordiko 7000, 6"). Wet etch using TechniEtch Al80 aluminium etchant was followed by a 2nd photolithography and the deposition of TiW(N) (300 Å) and Cu (300 Å) by ion beam deposition (Nordiko 3600, 8"). Liftoff, 3rd lithography, RF sputtering of Al₂O₃ (UHVII, 6") for electrode protection and electric passivation, 2nd liftoff and chip individualization (DISCO DAD 321, 6") followed. The portion of the electrodes in contact with the fluid are further stacked with a monolayer of graphene fabricated by PECVD (Aixtron Black Magic 2, 2"). The fabrication of the microfluidic channels, bridges for electrical actuation and inlet/outlet reservoirs was performed using a PDMS 3:1 120 μ m-thick membrane. Instead of molding the PDMS using conventional soft lithography through KLOE Kub 2 UV-Lithography system (4") in SU-8, as example, the PDMS was instead processed by xurography using a *Silhouette Curio* cutting printer after curing. This allowed to outline the microfluidic features and individualize the membrane. The same strategy was used to individualize the cellulose membrane acetate filters used within the pump to eliminate pressure-driven flow. The PDMS membrane was permanently bonded to the microfabricated Si chip (Harrick Plasma Cleaner PDC-002CE) and enclosed the cellulose membrane. The hybrid microfluidic pump was encased onto PMMA plates processed in a high precision 3 axis CNC SuperTech micromilling machine. Voltage was imposed to the electrical contacts of the pump through a custom made high-stability power supply.

All the steps for the identification of organ-on-a-chip models, simulation and microfabrication of the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump and of the design, fabrication and mounting of power supply are detailed in the sections below.

2 - IDENTIFICATION OF ORGAN-ON-A-CHIP MODELS

A multi-channel 3-D microfluidic cell culture chip of the size of a computer memory stick that simulates the activities, mechanical forces and physiological response of entire organs and organ systems is called an organ-on-a-chip. Building valid artificial organs requires not only a precise cellular manipulation, but a detailed understanding of fundamental intricate responses of the human body to any event. Organs that have been simulated by microfluidic devices include lung, intestine, heart, kidney, artery, bone, cartilage, skin, blood-brain barrier and more. They are essentially three-dimensional cross-sections of major functional units of whole living organs.

Organ-on-a-chip will allow to abolish the need for animals in drug development and toxin testing at the same time using lower fluids consumption (lower reagents costs, less waste), increased portability of the devices, increased process control (due to quicker thermo-chemical reactions) and decreased fabrication costs revolutionizing drug discovery, disease research and personalized medicine fields. The miniaturization of physical environment of living organs on chip leads to the usage of very small quantities of fluids, either body fluids or fluids of interest such as drugs, toxins, etc. Errors in the infusion of such nanoliter samples lead to failure in mimicking an organ's cellular properties in 3D culture models (biological activities, dynamic mechanical properties and biochemical functionalities).

The culture of tissues on organ-on-chips to successfully mimic the *in vivo* microenvironment requires the analysis of not only the nutrient intake of cells but also the flow and shear conditions of the system. An insufficient glucose concentration may compromise the viability of cells as well as the mechanisms implied in drug/microenvironment response. The same may be said about oxygen. As for shear stress, it can highly impact cell behaviour and communication by altering the cell form (e.g. making them round). This may happen if the shear stress is much higher or lower than the *in vivo* environment.

The data in the literature suggests that the kinetic reaction between cells and glucose (a key nutrient in cell growth) follows the Michaelis Menten model, which parameters depend on the type of cell and the initial concentration of glucose added to the assay system, both *in vivo* and inside the microsystem. Of course, the flow rate chosen must be adequate to favour the nutrient intake. As for the microfluidic systems, a tendency to use PDMS elastomer is visible, due to its permeability to gases, biocompatibility and cost-effectiveness. Some systems require the microfabrication of microporous membranes, which are usually made of PC, PTFE or PE thermoplastics. These materials are hydrophobic, which may compromise the adherence of cells to the microfluidic culture chambers. To overcome this problem, surfaces are functionalized with fibronectin, collagen (type I or IV) or laminin (extracellular matrix proteins). The cell density added to organ-on-chips varies between 6.71×10^4 and 9.98×10^4 cells/mL which, of course, depends on the dimensions of channels and culture chambers and/or membranes. Shear stress may vary between 2 mPa to 1.5 Pa, without compromising cell viability. These values were obtained with flow rates differing from 10 nL/min (minimum value found) and 2 mL/min. Residence time depends on the microfluidic structure fabricated (e.g. dimensions and shape), flow rate, cell type (cardiac, pancreatic, etc) and volume that occupies the structure. According to the previous data, residence time can vary from 7 s to 56 min. Table 1 summarizes the ranges.

Table 1. Identification of models for organ-on-a-chip and typical values [3-21]

Properties	Models/Typical Values
Kinetic Model for glucose (key nutrient)	Michaelis Menten: $\frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{J_{max} \cdot C_{glucose}}{K_M + C_{glucose}}$
Material for microfluidic device	PDMS (channels); PC, PTFE or PE thermoplastics (microporous membranes)
Surface Functionalization	fibronectin, collagen (type I or IV) or laminin
Cell density (cells/mL)	$6.71 \times 10^4 - 9.98 \times 10^4$
Shear stress, τ (mPa)	2 – 1500
Flow rates, Q (nL/min)	10 – 2000×10^3
Residence time, t (s)	7 – 3360

If ranges presented in Table 1 are respected when designing the organ-on-chip device, along with the appropriate choice of material and surface functionalization, cell viability can be assured, as long as nutrient and oxygen necessities are respected.

There is still the need to validate and optimize these systems and devise new calibration methods, conditions under which they are to be operated, the target uncertainty and best working practices. Since the human physiology consists of a dynamic environment, flow control is a crucial requirement of organs-on-a-chip. There is a great need for accurate and precise drug dosage that is both safe and effective at such small scales invaluable to tackle major technological challenges such as the simulation and reliable prediction of critical physiological response to drug administration.

3 - HYBRID MICROFLUIDIC MICROCHIP FLOW PUMP - DESIGN, SIMULATION and MICROFABRICATION

The microfluidic flow pump is fabricated using several materials:

- Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is one of the most used polymer in the microfabrication of microfluidic devices, as a result of its optical transparency, gas permeability, biocompatibility, and ease of fabrication and molding [22] The physical characteristics of PDMS depend highly on the monomer/curing agent ratio (typically 10:1) and curing temperature chosen, increasing the possibility of fabrication of structures (e.g. PDMS membranes) and range of applications [23].
- Graphene is becoming one of the most attractive materials in the field of microfabrication due to its exceptional mechanical, electrical, optical and thermal properties. It already has an enormous range of applications, from materials science, micro/nano processing to biomedicine and drug delivery [24-25]. In this work, graphene membranes are placed on top of the electrodes fabricated on the Si substrate to prevent direct contact of the electrodes with fluids introduced in the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump.
- Thermoplastics, specifically poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), are extensively used in microfluidics nowadays, due to their many advantages features, such as chemical stability, biocompatibility, low electrical conductivity, and wide range of design possibilities [26].

Furthermore, PMMA is a transparent, rigid substrate at room temperature, enabling the visualization of processes while attributing a robust character to microfluidic devices.

3.1 SIMULATION

The hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump is simulated in COMSOL Multiphysics 5.1, considering the geometry in Figure 1. The parameters of the flow are presented in Table 2.

Figure 1. Geometry considered in the simulations.

Table 2: Flow rate, voltage and geometric inputs for the simulations. Channel height is considered the same in all simulations to be $H_z = 120 \mu\text{m}$. The “in each cell is considering the value equal to that as found immediately above in the column.

<i>Geometry</i>	Q_{in}	$V_{bridge1}$	$V_{bridge2}$	$x_{bridge1}$	$x_{bridge2}$	x_{out}	a	$L_{bridge1}$	$L_{bridge2}$	$L_{pumping}$	$W_{bridge1}$	$W_{bridge2}$	$W_{pumping}$	$L_{V \rightarrow out}$	<i>Dimensions</i>
	[$\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$]	[V]	[V]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]
1	0	100	-20	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	2D, 3D
-	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0	10	-20	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D
-	-	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0	100	-120	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D
-	-	-	-420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0	-20	100	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D
-	-	-120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	0	-20	100	4.3	20.3	23	1	5.5	5.5	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D
-	-	-120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	0	-20	100	4.3	20.3	23	1	22	22	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D
-	-	-120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	0	-20	100	4.3	12.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	7.7	3D
-	-	-120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	-	-	-	-	19.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.7	-
6	-	-	-	-	21.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.7	-
7	0	-20	100	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.3	0.3	2	2.7	3D
8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.2	1.2	-	-	-
9	0	-20	100	4.3	20.3	23	0.5	11	11	23	0.3	0.3	1	2.7	3D
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-

The flow is modelled considering Newtonian fluid (water, liquid) of constant density and incompressible. Other conditions considered in the simulations are as follows:

Creeping flow, stationary, incompressible

$$0 = \nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)] + \mathbf{F} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

$$\rho\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Inlet: laminar inflow boundary condition - average velocity

$$L_{entr}\nabla_t \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla_t\mathbf{u} + (\nabla_t\mathbf{u})^T)] = -p_{entr}\mathbf{n} \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Outlet: pressure boundary condition, incompressible flow

$$[-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)]\mathbf{n} = -\hat{p}_0\mathbf{n} \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

$$\hat{p}_0 \leq p_0 \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

Wall: electro-osmotic velocity, tangential electric field, stationary

$$\mathbf{u} = u_{EO} \mathbf{E}_t, \quad u_{EO} = -\frac{\epsilon_r \epsilon_0 \zeta}{\mu}, \quad \mathbf{E}_t = \mathbf{E} - (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n} \quad \text{eq. 6}$$

The velocity term u_{EO} represents flow that balances viscous stresses with electrical forcing (electro-osmotic flow).

Electric currents, current conservation

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = Q_j \quad \text{eq. 7}$$

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_e \quad \text{eq. 8}$$

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla V \quad \text{eq. 9}$$

Electric field

Constitutive relation: Relative permittivity

$$\mathbf{D} = \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \quad \text{eq. 10}$$

Electric insulation

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0 \quad \text{eq. 11}$$

Figure 2 shows an example of mesh used in 3D simulations of Geometry 1 with dimensional variables found in Table 2.

Figure 2. Example of mesh used in 3D simulations of Geometry 1.

The velocity magnitude obtained for the outlet cut plane is presented in Figure 3. for the simulated conditions:

Geometry	Q_{in}	$V_{bridge1}$	$V_{bridge2}$	$x_{bridge1}$	$x_{bridge2}$	x_{out}	a	$L_{bridge1}$	$L_{bridge2}$	$L_{pumping}$	$W_{bridge1}$	$W_{bridge2}$	$W_{pumping}$	$L_{V \rightarrow out}$	Dimensions	$u_{meas,out}$	Q_{out}
	[$\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$]	[V]	[V]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]	[$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	[$\text{nL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$]
1	0	-420	-20	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	3D	1.01E-5	145

Figure 3. Velocity magnitude for cut plane @ $x = x_{out}$.

The flow rate is obtained from the surface averaged velocity and the channel cross section area as $Q_{out} = \frac{u_{average,out}}{A_{CS}}$. For the conditions above, $Q_{out} = 145 \text{ nL/min}$.

The flow velocity was then depicted in Figure 4a) represents the velocity values at $z = 1/2$ channel height for the geometric variables:

Geometry	Q_{in}	$V_{bridge1}$	$V_{bridge2}$	$x_{bridge1}$	$x_{bridge2}$	x_{out}	a	$L_{bridge1}$	$L_{bridge2}$	$L_{pumping}$	$W_{bridge1}$	$W_{bridge2}$	$W_{pumping}$	$L_{V \rightarrow out}$	Dimensions
	[$\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$]	[V]	[V]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]
1	10	100	-20	4.3	20.3	23	1	11	11	23	0.6	0.6	2	2.7	2D, 3D

considering the system represented in 2D and in 3D. Although the 2D representation of the flow field would significantly reduce the computational costs of simulations as well as system complexity, it can be seen from the figure that the 2D results (black dots) are common of a Poiseuille flow instead of the expected electroosmotic flow, leading to erroneous conclusions. Following studies were therefore performed considering 3D channel representations. Additionally, from Figure 4b, the flow rate in the 2D representation of the channel is failing to guarantee the mass balance, more noticeable for higher flow rates.

Figure 4. Results of velocity profiles in 2D vs 3D channels (Geometry 1).

The simulation of the 3D representation for the various flow rates, voltages and geometric inputs under study (Table 2) allowed to define the design to be fabricated. Main geometrical influences to the flow rate, obtained from the simulations results, are summarized here:

- $V_{bridge1}$ (cathode, -) $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \downarrow$
- L_{bridge} $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \downarrow$
- W_{bridge} $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \uparrow$
- $W_{pumping}$ $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \uparrow$
- $L_{V \rightarrow out}$ $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \downarrow$
- L_{pad} $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \uparrow$
- *Size (ratio)* $\uparrow \rightarrow Q_{out} \uparrow$

where \uparrow means increase and \downarrow means decrease.

3.2 MICROFABRICATION

The geometry of the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump is that defined in the simulations. The procedure for microfabrication has 6 main tasks (A-F) and is followed according to Figure 5.

Figure 5. Schematics of the fabrication steps.

Each of the 6 main tasks is described in the following sub-sections.

3.2 A. Individualization of cellulose membrane

A cellulose filter (pore size: 0.2 μm , diameter: 47 mm, thickness: 120 μm , GE Healthcare Whatman™) is used as the membrane material. The membrane shape is designed in AutoCAD and imported to the Silhouette Studio software (Figure 6a)) to be fabricated by xurography. The membrane is individualized on the Silhouette Curio cutting printer (Figure 6b)).

Figure 6. a) Design imported to the Silhouette Studio software and b) individualized cellulose membranes.

3.2 B. Fabrication and individualization of PDMS membrane

For the construction of the proposed hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump, a 120 μm thick PDMS membrane was fabricated by xurography and integrated in the system. The PDMS membrane covers the silicon/graphene substrate except the main reservoir, fluid channel, bridges, end channel, and electric contacts, as presented in Figure 7 in blue. The variables tested for the fabrication of the desired PDMS membrane are presented in Fig 8. To enable the precise design of the PDMS membrane without damaging the substrate, a ratio of 3:1 is used instead of the typical 10:1 ratio. Because of the need to cut the PDMS membrane with a specific design, the membrane cannot be directly spin coated on the Si/graphene substrate, as the cut could damage the Si substrate. Instead, the PDMS membrane was fabricated on a polystyrene plate, ensuring an adequate adhesion during the spin coating process without compromising any future step of peeling, and later transferred to the Si/graphene substrate.

Figure 7. Schematics of the coverage of PDMS membrane on silicon/graphene substrate.

Step 1. Substrate cleaning preparation

Step 2. PDMS preparation

Step 3. Spin coating and baking PDMS

Step 4. Xurography of the thin PDMS membrane

Figure 8. a) Schematic of the design cut into the PDMS membrane. The lines in red represent the lines followed by the blade of the printer; b) Xurography parameters for the fabrication of 120 μm PDMS membrane with Silhouette Curio and parameters for transfer procedure; c) Setup for the xurography fabrication. On top of the stage, two platforms are placed to secure the plate in place. A blade with size varying from 1 to 3 is used in the tests.

Step 5. Peel-off of PDMS membrane

3.2 C. Fabrication of chip with electrical contacts

The chip with electrical contacts for flow actuation is depicted in Fig 9.

Figure 9. a) schematics of the chip with electrical contacts. green: electrical contacts $\text{Al}_{98.5}\text{Si}_{1.0}\text{Cu}_{0.5}$ (3000Å); red: cellulose membrane; light blue: passivation layer (Al_2O_3 3000Å); dark blue: TiW (300Å) + Cu (300Å) + graphene (monolayer) and b) chip with electrical contacts after microfabrication Step 5.

The microfabrication steps to obtain the chip with electrical contacts for flow actuation were followed in order as:

Step 1: Substrate cleaning, wetbech, Cleanroom class 100

Step 2: AlSiCu (3000Å) deposition, Nordiko 7000 Magnetron sputtering system, Cleanroom class 100

Step 3: Photolithography Layer 2, Vapor prime/SVG track/Direct Write Laser/SVG track, Cleanroom class 10

Step 4: AlSiCu wet etching, wetbech, Cleanroom class 100

Step 5: Resist strip, wetbech, Cleanroom class 100

Step 6: Photolithography Layer 3, Vapor prime/SVG track/Direct Write Laser/SVG track, Cleanroom class 10

Step 7: TiW (300Å) + Cu (300Å) deposition, Nordiko 3600 ion beam deposition, Cleanroom class 100

Step 8: Lift off, wetbech, Cleanroom class 100

Step 9: Photolithography Layer 4, Vapor prime/SVG track/Direct Write Laser/SVG track, Cleanroom class 10

Step 10: AlOx (3000Å) deposition, UHV II sputtering system, Cleanroom class 10000

Step 11: Spin coating, SVG track, Cleanroom class 10

Step 11: Dicing, DAD Dicing Saw, Cleanroom class 10000

Step 12: Lift off, wetbech, Cleanroom class 100

Step 13.1: Graphene fabrication, Aixtron Black Magic 2, Cleanroom class 100

Step 13.2: Graphene transfer, Cleanroom class 10/100

1. Spin coating of 600 nm (x2) PMMA layer

Figure 10. The graphene/copper film is a) submitted to a spin coating process of PMMA 950, followed by a b) baking step at 160°C for 4 min.

2. Chemical etching of Cu film
3. Cleaning of the PMMA/graphene films
4. Removal of PMMA layer

a) **Figure 11.** The PMMA/graphene films are fished from DI water with the Si substrate: **a)** the graphene films + PMMA cover the electrodes defined in the Si substrate. **b)** Cleaning the sample with acetone and ethyl acetate removes the PMMA initially present, leaving only membranes of graphene (not visible to the naked eye) covering the electrodes.

3.2 D. Fabrication of PMMA support

In this work, two PMMA substrates (150 x 150 mm, 4 mm-thick) were fabricated with specific designs for top and bottom casings (e.g. pocket, inlet, and outlet structures) to encase the silicon chip with electrical contacts, cellulose membrane and PDMS membrane.

Step 1. AutoCAD design (Fig 12)

Figure 12. Schematics of the a) top plate and b) bottom plate of the PMMA casing in AutoCAD for the encapsulation of the silicon substrate. The top casing presents inlets to contact the main reservoir and the electrodes of the system, an outlet, and perforations to unite the two PMMA plates. The bottom casing includes a pocket structure and perforations aligned with the ones present in the top casing.

Step 2. Substrate cleaning and preparation

Step 3. Microfabrication of the top and bottom casings (drill, endmill, engrave, SuperTech milling machine)

Step 4. Casing preparation (Fig 13)

Figure 13: PMMA casing for the casing of the silicon substrate: a) top plate and bottom plate after the milling/drilling process and b) with Teflon screws in place.

3.2 E. Bonding

The transfer layer/PDMS membrane complex obtained in **B** and the silicon/graphene substrate obtained in **C** are placed in an oxygen plasma equipment and submitted to a plasma activation process for 5 min at high intensity (Plasma Cleaner PDC-002CE, Harrick Plasma). The PDMS and silicon substrates are bonded as depicted in Fig 14.

Figure 14. PDMS permanently bonded to the Si substrate. In this example, the Si is not microfabricated.

3.2 F. Assemblage

All the elements are assembled to obtain the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump as shown in Fig 15.

Figure 15. Hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump.

4 POWER SUPPLY MODULE - DESIGN, FABRICATION, MOUNTING and OPERATION

The power supply module of this setup is built around the Bellnix OHV12-1.0K1500P, an ultracompact, ultralow ripple noise DC-DC converter. This component accepts a nominal input voltage of 12 V and outputs a fully adjustable voltage from 0 to 1000 V, with a maximum output power of 1.5 W. The relevant electric specs of this converter are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Nominal operating parameters of OHV12-1.0K1500P DC-DC converter.

OHV12-1.0K1500P

Input voltage (V_{DC})	11.0 – 13.0
Output voltage (V_{DC})	0 – +1000
Output current (mA)	0 – 1.5
Minimum load resistance ($k\Omega$)	666.7
Typical input current (A)	0.28
Typical ripple noise (mVpp)	5

In the complete power supply module, additional components are added both to the input and output sides of the OHV12 converter to enhance its operating characteristics. In addition, a resistor network is employed to change the control voltage that defines the output voltage of the converter. The electric schematic of the power supply module is shown in Fig 16, and The PCB fabricated is depicted in Fig 17.

Figure 16. a) Electric schematic of the MeDD II high-voltage power supply module and b) image of the fabricated PCB before component soldering.

The casing of the power supply was fabricated by 3D printing

Figure 17. a) Isometric view of the MeDD II power supply housing CAD drawing and b) Top view of the MeDD II power supply housing CAD drawing.

4.1 OPERATION INSTRUCTIONS

The operation of this power supply is generally simple and self-explanatory, due to the small number of operator adjustments necessary. Nevertheless, the following safety warnings and instructions should be read carefully prior to operating the power supply.

4.1.1. Install the power supply

ALL SWITCHES MUST BE SET TO THE **OFF** POSITION BEFORE START

1. Place the power supply in a stable, levelled surface.
2. Connect the output power plugs to the colour coded sockets in the power supply. Plug the other end to the hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump (the polarity will influence the flow direction).
3. Plug in the 12 V transformer-rectifier.

4.1.2. Turn ON and operate the power supply

DO NOT SHORT-CIRCUIT THE HIGH-VOLTAGE OUTPUT TERMINALS

DO NOT CONNECT OR DISCONNECT TERMINALS WHILE SWITCHES ARE **ON**

1. Turn the main power switch ON. The OHV12, LCD voltmeter and cooling fan will be powered on.
2. Select the intended output voltage using the rotary selector. The first position corresponds to an output voltage of 100 V, the second position to 200 V and so on; the last position corresponds to 500 V. The feedback of the selected output voltage is given after the high-voltage switch is turned ON.
3. Turn the high-voltage switch ON. The feedback of the selected output voltage is now given.
4. The hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump stabilizes around 1000 - 2000 s, considering the relative voltage difference to be $RVD = (x_2 - x_1)/x_1$, where x_1 is the set value and x_2 is the read value and its derivative over time $dRVD/dt$ to be lower than 5×10^{-6} (Fig 158).
5. To change the output voltage, change the position of the rotary selector. While it is not necessary to turn the high-voltage switch OFF before changing the selector position, the output voltage will fluctuate during the commutation time. In addition, avoid leaving the selector knob in-between positions.

Figure 18. Stabilization times for [100:100:500] V imposed to the Hybrid microfluidic microchip flow pump. The relative voltage difference is equal to $(x_2-x_1)/x_1$, where x_2 and x_1 are the read value and the set value, respectively.

4.1.3. Turn OFF the power supply

1. Turn the high-voltage switch OFF.
2. Place the rotary selector in position 1.
3. Turn the main power switch OFF. The OHV12, LCD voltmeter and cooling fan will be powered off.

5 NOTATION

D	Electric displacement	$[\text{C.m}^{-2}]$
E	Electric field vector	$[\text{V.m}^{-1}]$
E	Electric field	$[\text{V.m}^{-1}]$
E_t	Electric field, tangential component	$[\text{V.m}^{-1}]$
F	Volume force	$[\text{N.m}^{-3}]$
J	Current density (volume)	$[\text{A.m}^{-2}]$
J_e	Externally generated current density	$[\text{A.m}^{-2}]$
L_{entr}	Length of fictitious	$[\text{m}]$
n	Boundary normal pointing out of the domain	$[-]$
n	Boundary normal pointing out of the domain	$[-]$
p	Pressure	$[\text{Pa}]$

p_{entr}	Pressure at the fictitious entrance	[Pa]
\hat{p}_0	Pressure at the outlet with suppressed backflow	[Pa]
p_0	Pressure at the outlet	[Pa]
Q_j	Current source	[A.m ⁻³]
\mathbf{u}	Velocity	[m.s ⁻¹]
u_{EO}	Electro-osmotic mobility	[m ² .V ⁻¹ .s ⁻¹]
V	Electric potential	[V]
<i>Greek symbols</i>		
ϵ_0	Permittivity of vacuum $\approx \frac{1}{36\pi} 10^{-9}$	[F.m ⁻¹]
ϵ_0	Permittivity of vacuum $\approx \frac{1}{36\pi} 10^{-9}$	[F.m ⁻¹]
ϵ_r	Relative permittivity	[-]
ϵ_r	Relative permittivity of the material	[-]
ζ	Zeta potential	[V]
μ	Dynamic viscosity	[Pa.s]
ρ	Volumetric mass density	[kg.m ⁻³]
σ	Electrical conductivity	[S.m ⁻¹]
<i>Mathematical symbols</i>		
\mathbf{I}	Identity matrix	
∇_t	Tangential gradient	

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